

USING AND TEACHING A DIGITAL WORDS

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Abstract: In the article is shown rising and development of information technology has offered a better pattern to explore the new teaching models. As a result technology plays a very important role in English teaching. This paper tries to analyze problems faced by using technologies in language teaching.

Key words: English Language Teaching, multimedia technology, advantages, disadvantages, optimization, strategies. The new era assigns new challenges and duties on the modern teacher. The tradition of English teaching has been drastically changed with the remarkable entry of technology. Technology provides so many options as making teaching interesting and also making teaching more productive in terms of improvements. Technology is one of the most significant drivers of both social and linguistic change. As the use of English has increased in popularity so has the need for qualified teachers to instruct students in the language.

Introduction: Digital words, also known as digital text or electronic text, refer to text-based information that is stored and transmitted electronically in a digital format. This includes documents, articles, e-books, emails, social media posts, websites, and other forms of written content that exist in digital form. It can be easily accessed, shared, edited, and searched using various digital devices such as computers, smartphones, and e-readers. They have become a primary mode of communication and information sharing in the digital age, replacing or supplementing traditional print-based media. However, offer several advantages over their printed counterparts. They can be easily replicated and distributed at a low

cost, making information more widely available. They can also be easily modified, updated, and corrected. Moreover, digital text can be presented in various formats, allowing for interactivity, multimedia integration, and accessibility features. Digital words also play a crucial role in the field of natural language processing (NLP) and artificial intelligence (AI), as they serve as input for various language-based algorithms and models. These technologies enable tasks such as language translation, sentiment analysis, text summarization, and chat bot interactions.

Overall, digital words have revolutionized the way we create, consume, and interact with written information, shaping the modern digital landscape. It is true that there are teachers who use 'cutting edge' technology, but the majority of teachers still teach in the traditional manner. None of these traditional manners are bad or damaging the students. In fact, till date they are proving to be useful also. However, there are many more opportunities for students to gain confidence practice and extend themselves, especially for ESL students who learn the language for more than just fun. For them to keep pace with ELT and gain more confidence they have to stride into the world of multimedia technology. Nowadays, the stereotyped traditional teaching methods and environment are unpopular while multimedia technology featuring audio, visual animation effects naturally and humanely makes us more access to information besides, with such characteristics as abundant-information and crossing time and space, multimedia technology offers a sense of reality and functions very well, which greatly cultivates students' interest and motivation in study and their involvement in class activities. In addition, multimedia teaching is also flexible. It is obvious that the context can be created not only in the classroom, but also after class.

Multimedia language teaching can also create a multimedia language environment for the purpose of conducting language teaching. English teaching itself must focus on the guidance of teachers and be student centered (Holec), which we believe is one of the principles for language teaching. Students are bound to have some problems in classroom teaching, which can be addressed under the guidance

of teachers. In such circumstances, students can use the new technology to their advantage, such as manipulating the network to contact teachers, and receiving answers by email. In spite of advantages of application of multimedia technology to English class teaching has to improve teaching effect and students' overall capacities, there are many issues existing in practical teaching, such as:

Main part:1.English language and English analysis by the teachers are effective in conveying knowledge to the students from English pronunciation to comprehension, improving students' English thought patterns and oral expression, Whereas, the introduction of multimedia technology featuring audio, visual, textual effect fully meets audio and visual requirements of the students and enhance their interest, but it also results in of communication between teachers and students, replacement of teachers' voice by computer sound, and teachers' analysis by visual image and students have' few chances for speaking communication. With the favorable atmosphere by the mutual communication between teachers and students fading away, and sound and image of multimedia affecting students' initiative to think and speak, English class turns to course ware show and students are made viewers rather than the participants of class activities.

2.It is clear that language teaching is different from science subjects, for language teaching does not require demonstration by various steps, rather, the tense and orderly atmosphere is formed through questions and answer between teachers and students, Teachers raise real-time questions and guide the students to think, cultivate their capacity to discover and solve problems, however, due to over demonstration and prearranged order, the courseware lacks real-time effect and cannot give feedback. It ignores emphasis and importance in teaching; it also neglects instruction in students' thinking, inspiring their paths of thinking, strengthening their capacity contemplating and solving problems. In this way, it should be noted that cultivation of students' thinking capacity should be the major objective in teaching and using of multimedia technology and it should not take up the students' time for thinking, analyzing and exploring questions.

3.It is proved through practice that adequate application of multimedia technology to teaching can make breakthroughs in class teaching. That is to say, during multimedia assisting teaching, teachers still play the leading role that their position could never be replaced by the computer. For instance, the introduction to each lesson and speaking communication are good way to improve students' listening and speaking which the computer cannot fulfill. Therefore, teachers' interpretation will not be overlooked. Meanwhile, as a practical linguistic science, English should be used very often in class to cultivate the students' communicative competence, Multimedia, as an instrument for assisting teaching, serves the teachers despite it extraordinary effect, So teaching determines whether to adopt multimedia technology. Otherwise, the teachers were acting as the projectionist, clicking the screen.

4.The function of multimedia assisting in teaching cannot be replaced by many other instruments, which does not mean that multimedia can replace any other form of instrument; Some teachers tend to entirely depend on multimedia teaching. While, it should be noticed that although multimedia has its unique advantages in teaching, the characteristics functions of other forms of teaching instruments are still incomparable. For example, the recorder still plays a role in broadcasting listening material. So teachers are supposed to choose appropriate media and instrument based on the requirements of teaching and integrate multimedia instrument with traditional one and fully perform their merits, rather than merely in pursuit of trendy method. Concerning the development of technology, we believe that in future, the use of multimedia language teaching will be further enhanced. The process of English learning will be more student-centered but less time-consuming. The use of digital words is subjective and can vary depending on different contexts and situations. However, there are some general guidelines and considerations to keep in mind when it comes to allowing the use of digital words:

1. Clear communication: Digital words should be used to enhance clarity and understanding of the message being conveyed. They should not hinder comprehension or create confusion.

2. Relevance: The use of digital words should be relevant to the content or context in which they are being used. They should add value or serve a purpose in conveying the intended meaning.

3. Audience appropriateness: Consider the intended audience and their familiarity with digital words or technology-related terms. Ensure that the level of technicality aligns with the audience's understanding and doesn't alienate or confuse them.

4. Accessibility: Ensure that the use of digital words doesn't create accessibility barriers for individuals with disabilities. For example, avoid using acronyms or technical terms without providing explanations or alternatives for those who may be unfamiliar.

5. Cultural sensitivity: Be aware of cultural differences and avoid using digital words that may be offensive, inappropriate, or exclusive to certain groups.

6. Contextual limitations: Understand the limitations of using digital words in certain contexts such as formal writing, academic settings, or professional communication, where a more traditional or standardized language may be preferred.

Ultimately, the appropriateness of using digital words will depend on the specific situation, audience, and purpose of communication. It's important to strike a balance between incorporating digital words for clarity and relevance while considering the needs and understanding of the intended audience.

Conclusion: Therefore, it promises that the teaching quality will be improved and students' applied English skill can be effectively cultivated, meaning that students' communicative competence will be further developed. The users of innovative technology rethink before utilizing, taking only benefits from them.

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